

COST ASSESSMENT OF CARBON-REINFORCED COMPOSITE AUTOMOTIVE PART

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SUMMARY: The application of composites, primarily glass-fiber reinforced thermoset polymers, remains predominantly in non-structural elements of an automobile today. Carbon-fiber composites are an alternative to glass-fiber composites because they are stiffer and have greater weight reduction potential (i.e., 60-70% relative to steel), and therefore have better potential for structural applications. Development of designs and production techniques for a composite-intensive body-in-white (BIW) structure offering a minimum of 60% weight savings over steel at a cost close to steel's, while meeting manufacturing, assembly, crashworthiness, and performance objectives is currently underway by the Automotive Composites Consortium (ACC) – a collaborative, pre-competitive R&D partnership, in collaboration with the U.S. Department of Energy's Office of FreedomCAR and Vehicle Technologies Automotive Lightweighting Program. This paper addresses the economic viability of a carbon-reinforced composite automotive part, which is one of the major obstacles in the large scale application of automotive composites in the industry today. Development of a cost modeling framework for examining the economic viability of various manufacturing options for producing composite BIW parts, including the cost estimation of a complete BIW is discussed here. A specific BIW part (i.e., body side inner) using P4 and SRIM as preforming and molding technologies, respectively, is considered here as a demonstration of this modeling framework.

The baseline production cost of a body side inner is estimated to be \$88.53/part, where material contribution was the highest, i.e., 60% of total cost. A significant reduction in carbon fiber cost is anticipated to lower the part cost, from \$113.86 to \$63.21 due to a reduction from \$8/lb to \$2/lb. Besides material cost, other factors, i.e., production volume and cycle time, previously found to be detrimental to the economic viability of composites were found to be applicable in this case also. A minimum production cost was achieved around annual production volume of 75K, and a cycle time of 2 min. instead of 3.5 min would lower the part cost from \$88.53 to \$75.33. A part cost range of \$59.58–\$140.87 was estimated when the five key input variables were maintained at their low and high values. It is suggested that the economic viability of automotive carbon-reinforced composites is incomplete without further consideration of a complete BIW cost assessment as the part-by-part substitution fails to capture the part consolidation and the net-shape processing characteristics of composite

KEYWORDS: carbon fiber, automotive composite, cost, body side inner, manufacturing technology.

INTRODUCTION

The application of composites, primarily glass-fiber-reinforced thermoset polymers, remains predominantly in non-structural elements of the automotive vehicle. Carbon-fiber composites are an alternative to glass-fiber composites because they are stiffer and have greater weight reduction potential (i.e., 60-70% relative to steel) and therefore have better potential for structural applications. Carbon fiber composites' most significant use to date has been in concept cars. For example, they were used in the Ford Granada about two decades ago, in General Motors 1991 Ultralite concept vehicle, and in the

prestige car and racing car industry such as McLaren F1. The automaker BMW has recently announced its plan to make lightweight carbon-fiber-reinforced car bodies under production conditions by 2005 for its recently unveiled Z22 concept vehicle, the full-sized passenger vehicle based on the 528i sport wagon [1].

Several developmental programs are currently underway to explore the potential of carbon-fiber-reinforced composite ultra lightweight vehicle structures. The hypercar design concept by Rocky Mountain Institute is focused on the optimization of whole system design to capture the synergies of ultralight construction using advanced composites monocoque body and chassis, low-drag design, hybrid electric drive, and efficient accessories to achieve 3- to 5-fold improvement in fuel economy and maintain or improve upon vehicle performance, safety, amenities, and affordability of today's vehicles [2]. In the United Kingdom, a carbon fiber composite ultra lightweight vehicle structure for the Aero-stable carbon car is under development. It uses a novel form of textile preform laminated to form a single-piece integrated-frame structure [3]. All these efforts are targeted at improving the commercial viability of carbon fiber-reinforced composites by near net-shape parts consolidation that will reduce the effect of high carbon fiber cost and long cycle times.

The Automotive Composites Consortium (ACC) which is a collaborative, pre-competitive R&D partnership, in collaboration with the Department of Energy's (DOE) Office of FreedomCAR and Vehicle Technologies Automotive Lightweighting Materials (ALM) program, has laid and initiated plans to develop designs and production techniques for a composite-intensive body-in-white (BIW) structure [4]. The project objective is to design, analyze, and build a composite-intensive BIW offering a minimum of 60% weight savings over steel at a cost close to steel's, while meeting manufacturing, assembly, crashworthiness, and performance objectives. To accomplish this objective, the project has been divided into three key phases during which mass, cost, and performance will be addressed by evaluating a broad range of processes and materials systems. Carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer composites (primarily random-chopped carbon fibers) have been considered for the BIW concept chosen for Phase 1 of the program because they meet the severe weight reduction goal. The mass of the BIW is predicted to be 88 kg, 66% less than a steel BIW. The total number of BIW parts is less than 20.

Although it is likely that a range of high-volume processes suited for specific parts will be used eventually for this ACC composite-intensive BIW program, powdered preforming (P4) and structural reaction injection molding (SRIM) processes have been under initial consideration. The major focus of this paper is to provide the initial cost assessment of a specific BIW part (i.e., body side inner) based on the limited available data on P4 and SRIM as preforming and molding technologies, respectively. The cost assessment should not be construed as an accurate assessment of absolute part cost but rather will provide the bases for cost sensitivity analysis and comparison with other processes. Development of a cost modeling framework for examining the economic viability of various manufacturing options for producing composite BIW parts, including the cost estimation of a complete BIW is also being discussed here.

The next two sections provide a brief description of the P4/SRIM technology and the cost estimation approach used here. Results are discussed in the following section, while the major conclusions are laid out in the last section of this paper.

P4 and SRIM DESCRIPTION

The P4 process, invented by a subsidiary of Owens Corning Fiberglass, is a large-scale, low-cost, low-scrap, high-volume (50K units/year), fully automated preforming process. It involves choppers mounted on robots that spray short strands of fibers, applied along with powdered binder, onto a screen to make the preformed shape. Once the preform is made using at first hot air flow through the screen for melting the

binder followed by ambient air flow for solidifying the binder and setting the preform, it is lifted out and placed in a mold where it is injected with a liquid resin that solidifies to make a rigid composite part. The P4 process is yet to be demonstrated for commercial carbon fiber applications, but it is already being used in an evaluation program sponsored by the Air Force for aerospace structures [5], albeit at very slow cycle times and low volumes; and it has a tremendous potential for e-glass and carbon fiber applications [6].

Although SRIM molding process was initially considered suitable only for parts of modest size, the process is suitable now for a wide range of structural and semi-structural components in the heavy truck and automotive industries, including load floors, floor pans, and cross members. SRIM is a promising process for the manufacture of composite structures that have a high degree of part consolidation, a factor that improves their cost-effectiveness relative to stamped metal structures. In this process, a preform is placed in a matched metal mold and a low-viscosity resin is rapidly injected. The resin quickly impregnates the fibers and within seconds begins to crosslink to form the rigid polymer matrix.

This P4/SRIM technology has been successfully demonstrated in an earlier ACC-led program, designated focal project 2, for the production of a composite pickup truck box. The technology produced boxes at a rate of one every 4 minutes, and the boxes met all performance criteria, saved 25% in weight, and costed no more than a comparable steel structure. A version of this technology was used to produce composite pickup boxes available in General Motors 2001 Chevy Silverado (manufactured by Meridian Automotive Systems, Inc.) and for three large, semi-structural components in Ford's low-volume Aston Martin Vanquish model. General Motors also uses this technology to manufacture the mid-gate modules and the inner tailgate sections for the popular Chevrolet Avalanche and the recently introduced Cadillac Escalade EXT hybrid sport utility vehicle [7].

COST MODELING FRAMEWORK AND APPROACH

A spreadsheet-based modeling framework was developed for the BIW cost estimation. This framework is an enhancement of the earlier one developed for the ACC-led focal project 2 for the pickup truck box cost estimation [8]. Figure 1 shows the cost estimation framework developed for the complete BIW composite cost estimation. The manufacturing process selection is made at the BIW part level, allowing a combination of various manufacturing processes for various BIW parts to estimate the complete BIW cost. Some BIW parts are grouped into categories of parts (as shown later as an example in Figure 2) having similar cycle time based on similar characteristics such as surface area and weight. These groupings allow for a simpler cost estimation and take advantage of process economics, e.g., sharing similar capital equipment among parts. It may be desirable in some instances to do this grouping at the individual production steps, i.e., preforming, molding, and trimming. Figure 2 shows the preliminary user front-end developed based on this framework for the complete BIW cost estimation. After selecting the part manufacturing process, the user can easily change the baseline data available in the model to reflect a particular manufacturing environment. The framework structure is designed to be dynamic, i.e., part-manufacturing processes can easily be added as they are developed and come under consideration.

A BIW part-manufacturing technology in this framework is represented as a sequence of three production steps, i.e., preforming, molding, and trimming. The user of the framework selects the specific technology for the preforming and molding steps. As minimal non-automatic trimming of shear edges with hand held grinders for the SRIM molded parts is being considered here, the user interface doesn't provide explicitly the trimming options in this case. The output of the first production step—in terms of total cost and the

Figure 1. Structure of cost estimation framework for BIW.

Figure 2. User front-end of the cost modeling framework.

cost of individual inputs—becomes an input to subsequent production steps. Thus, the framework allows the user to estimate how different manufacturing technologies selected at early production steps affect total cost. The approach takes into account the technical and economic parameters for the production-step cost estimation, and the production method is assumed to be in-house and transferred at cost. For each production step, the total cost of the product at that step, the contribution of that production step to the total cost of the product at that point in the production, and the contribution of each input to the total cost and to the cost of a particular production step are estimated. A spreadsheet modeling framework provides flexibility in conducting sensitivity analyses with respect to key technology and cost parameters. Demonstration of this framework is limited here to the cost estimation of a specific BIW part, i.e., body side inner.

For a specific part manufacturing process, the major inputs to each production step are materials, capital, energy, labor, and floor space. The production facility is assumed to be a “tier 2/3”-level, dedicated, new production facility involved in similar manufacturing operations. Capital and

FOCAL PROJECT III
Composite-Intensive Body Structure Cost Modeling

	Part Weight (lbs)	Preforming	Molding/Trimming	Change Data?	Part Cost (Default part costs calculated at a production volume of 50K/yr)
Tower Piece	2.4	P4	SRIM	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	\$
Front Header	1.1	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Rear Header	1.2	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Upper Dash Panel	4.3	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Radiator Panel	2.3	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Body SideThird (LH, RH)	8.0	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Rear Quarter Panel (LH, RH)	7.4	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Front Wheel Arch (LH, RH)	11.2	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Rear Long (LH, RH)	11.9	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Dash Panel	11.0	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Parcel Shelf	9.0	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Body Side Inner (LH)	16.6	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Body Side Inner (RH)	16.6	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Body Side Outer (LH)	22.7	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Body Side Outer (RH)	22.7	P4	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Front Lower Long (LH, RH)	4.5	AGFM	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Roof	9.0	AGFM	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Rear Floor	14.9	AGFM	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Front Floor	16.9	AGFM	SRIM	<input type="radio"/>	\$
Subtotal Body-in-White Cost					\$ -
Assembly					\$
Total Body-in-White Cost					\$

facility (i.e., cell size) costs are calculated as the function of annual production volume, cycle time, and the product of production step yields, where the latter is defined as the fraction of non-defective parts manufactured at the production step. The production lines are added with the increase in production volume to maintain the given hourly production rate. In addition to capital,

material, and facility, other direct costs such as labor and energy are calculated based on the hourly unit cell usage and part production rate. Indirect labor cost is assumed to be a fixed percentage of direct labor cost; whereas most other indirect costs such as corporate allocation, sales, general and administrative expenses, and sales markup considered in the cost estimation occur at the final production step.

Table 1 shows the baseline major input data assumptions for the body side inner part by three major production steps, i.e., preforming, molding, and trimming, under annual part production volume of 100K parts. The latter production volume has been considered as the baseline in our sensitivity analysis discussed later in this paper. As mentioned earlier, P4 and SRIM technologies are considered here for preforming and molding, respectively; whereas, minimal non-automatic hand held grinding for trimming. The body side inner is assumed to be 16.6 lbs, using polyurethane as the resin matrix material with a carbon fiber loading of 50 wt%. The only changes in the baseline input data assumptions with different production volumes considered are in capital equipment cost and facility size, because a dedicated production facility is assumed. All capital equipment costs listed in this table include the cost of racks, material handling, etc. The post mold machining—different from trimming—which requires holes, cutouts, etc. for the part has not been considered in this analysis. Since the focus of this cost assessment is on the cost sensitivity to various technical and economic production parameters, only BIW part production cost is being estimated here without consideration of any corporate expenses which include its overhead, sales, general and administrative expenses, and sales markup.

RESULTS

The baseline production cost of a body side inner is currently estimated to be \$88.53 for an annual production volume of 100K parts. Material contributes more than 60% to total part cost as shown in Figure 3. A significantly higher material contribution at this high production volume is consistent with earlier findings in the literature [9-10]. Other major cost contributors are capital and energy, where the former also includes the tooling cost. The facility and compliance costs are included in the “other” category as shown in this figure. Capital cost contribution was found to be higher than labor cost (21% vs. 13%), most likely due to significantly higher level of investments

Input Parameter	Value	Input Parameter	Value
<i>Preforming</i>		<i>Trimming</i>	
Process Time (min)	3.5	Process Time (min)	2
Preform Weight (lbs)	8.3	Trimming Scrap Rate (%)	1.0%
Carbon Fiber Cost (\$/lb)	\$5.00	No. Labor at Cell	2.0
Fiber Loading (wt. %)	50.0%	Trimming Energy Usage (kW-hr/cell hr)	12
Binder Cost (\$/lb)	\$2.74	<i>Business Variables</i>	
Scrap rate (%)	3.0%	Burdened Labor Rate (\$/hr)	\$26.00
No. Labor at Cell	2.0	Indirect Personnel (% Direct Labor)	40%
Preform Energy Usage (kW-hr/cell hr)	150.0	Energy Cost (\$/kw-hr)	\$0.06
Preform Tooling Cost (\$)	\$150,000	Capital I & M Cost (% Capital)	3.0%
Preform Tooling Life (# parts)	500,000	SG&A Rate (%)	0.0%
<i>Molding</i>		Sales Markup Rate (%)	0.0%
Press Size (tons)	1,000	<i>Capital Costs</i>	
Process Time (min)	3.5	P4 Cell (\$)	\$3,000,000
Resin Wt (lbs)	8.3	SRIM Cell (\$)	\$5,200,000
Resin Cost (\$/lb)	\$1.25	Trimming Cell (\$)	\$80,000

Tooling Cost (\$)	\$750,000	Interest Rate (%)	7.0%
Molding Tooling Life (# of parts)	500,000	Capital Payback Period (yrs)	8
Molding Scrap Rate (%)	3.0%	Tooling Payback Period (yrs)	3
No. Labor at Cell	2.0		
Molding Energy Usage (kW- hr/cell hr)	156.0		

Table 1. Baseline Major Input Data Assumptions for Body Side Inner at Production Volume of 100K/year

Figure 3. Baseline body side inner cost distribution

necessary for P4 preforming in this case. Some of these major cost contributors have been further analyzed through sensitivity analyses, where a single input variable was varied while baseline values were maintained for the other input variables.

Because material costs contribute a major share of total part cost, the sensitivity of total cost to carbon fiber cost was examined (Figure 4.) The cost sensitivity in this figure is shown both in terms of part cost and \$/lb. The part cost increases linearly by \$8.44 per \$1 increase in carbon fiber cost. With a reduction in current carbon fiber cost of \$8/lb to \$4/lb, the part cost is estimated to decrease from \$113.86/part to \$80.09/part. The corresponding costs in terms of (\$/lb) are \$6.86 and \$4.82. These unit costs are considerable higher than the conventional steel part cost, which is usually in the range of \$1–\$2/lb based on a general rule-of-thumb. This cost of material substitution comparison may or may not be valid for a steel part like body side inner (in one piece) due to its extreme forming complexity. It is also important to consider the complete BIW instead of part-by-part substitution — where part consolidation and net shape processing

characteristics of composites can be taken into consideration—to understand the savings potential of carbon fiber parts. Even at a systems-level cost comparison, the value of weight savings

Figure 4. Body side inner cost sensitivity to carbon-fiber cost.

offered by these materials is detrimental to its overall economic viability. The range of value of weight savings commonly accepted by the automotive industry is \$1-\$4/lb, which takes into account life cycle fuel savings resulting from primary and secondary weight savings that lightweight materials provide.

Figure 5 shows the body side inner cost sensitivity to annual production volume. At higher volumes, with investment costs spread over a large number of parts and the material price as the dominant and invariant cost factor, the part cost declines. A sharp reduction in part cost from \$307.75 to \$92.31 is estimated as annual production volume increases from 5K to 50K. The minimum part cost is achieved around 75K parts/year. The part cost is shown to be fairly stable beyond this production volume of 75K parts/year at around \$85/part as tooling cost in addition to investment cost gets amortized over a large number of parts. Because a dedicated production facility is assumed, there is some sharp increase in the part cost where there exists underutilization of the facility, but this sharpness reduces with annual production volume as it gets spread over a large number of parts. This erratic behavior is due to the fact that as production increases require the purchase of additional equipment, the part cost increases sharply and then decays until that additional capital is fully utilized.

Fig. 5 Body Side Inner Cost Sensitivity to Annual Production Volume

The body side inner cost sensitivity to five key variables is shown in Figure 6. The range of part cost values shown for each variable indicates the sensitivity of the part’s total cost to that variable alone. Other parameters are maintained at baseline values, shown in Table 1. The lower and upper part cost values correspond to the parameter values shown within the parenthesis. The mid-value within the parenthesis corresponds to the baseline parameter value as shown in Table 1. The y-axis represents the baseline part cost, i.e., \$88.53. Figure 6 shows, as discussed before, that the part cost is greatly sensitive to carbon fiber cost. The part cost is sensitive to fiber loading, but its range is found to be \$82.14–\$95.24/part for the narrow fiber loading range of 40– 60 weight % considered here, compared to \$63.21–\$113.86/part for the range of \$2/lb–\$8/lb of carbon fiber. Similarly, as shown before in Figure 5, the part cost range due to the given production volume range is fairly small, i.e., \$82.99–\$92.31/part, the most of which is contributed at a lower production volume.

Figure 6. Body Side Inner Cost Sensitivity to Key Input Variables

The cycle time effect shown in Figure 6 is significant. The values for cycle times apply to both preforming and molding production steps. As cycle time also affects the labor and energy, as well as capital equipment required for the number of production lines to meet the hourly production rate, the part cost range was found to be \$75.33–\$93.55 for the range of values considered here. Due to significantly lower contribution of labor and energy costs to part cost, their effects were not substantially higher than the production volume effects as observed earlier. Process yield is the percentage of non-defective parts manufactured. For this sensitivity analysis it is assumed that variation in process yield occurs only at the preforming and molding steps; no variation is assumed for the trimming. The values for the process yield are derived as the product of each of the three process steps. Although process yield would effect all major part cost categories (i.e., material, capital, energy, and labor), its effect on the part cost range is estimated to be low (i.e., \$86.30-\$92.15) due to a narrow range of values considered here. The body side inner cost was estimated to be in the range of \$59.58–\$140.87, when considering together all the above five key

input variable values at their lower and upper end.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides a cost modeling framework to estimate the cost of fiber-reinforced polymer composite automotive BIW. Demonstration of this framework was made by providing a preliminary cost estimate of a carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer composite BIW part, i.e., body side inner, using P4/SRIM manufacturing technology. With the availability of more data, the developed framework can easily be expanded for the economic comparison of competing manufacturing technologies for a specific BIW part and the estimation of a complete BIW cost using a combination of various different manufacturing technologies for various BIW parts. It is envisioned that the utility of the cost model is most beneficial in determining the most cost sensitive process and material parameters, and in assessing the relative cost-effectiveness of various processes. Identifying the most sensitive parameter will aid in defining research directions.

The baseline production cost of a body side inner is estimated to be \$88.53/part, where material contribution was the highest, i.e., 60% of total cost. A significant reduction in carbon fiber cost is anticipated to lower the part cost, from \$113.86 to \$63.21 due to a reduction from \$8/lb to \$2/lb. Besides material cost, other factors, i.e., production volume and cycle time, previously found to be detrimental to the economic viability of composites were found to be applicable in this case also. A minimum production cost was achieved around annual production volume of 75K, and a cycle time of 2 min. instead of 3.5 min would lower the part cost from \$88.53 to \$75.33. A part cost range of \$59.58–\$140.87 was estimated when the five key input variables were maintained at their low and high values.

Note that the production cost estimates presented here do not include corporate expenses and the estimates are applicable to the specific assumptions about the input data made in this analysis here. Even with a significant reduction in carbon fiber cost, per-pound production cost of carbon-reinforced polymer composite body side inner may not be cost-effective compared to the similar conventional steel part. It is possible that due to the extreme forming complexity for the part like body side inner (in one piece), per-pound production cost comparison basis may be different than what assumed here. But an examination of the economic viability a single BIW part using a specific manufacturing technology does not provide a complete assessment of economic viability of using carbon-fiber reinforced polymer composites for BIW. A part-by-part substitution is not a fair comparison in this case because it fails to capture the part consolidation and the net-shape processing characteristics of composites. It is appropriate to consider the complete BIW even if considering only a single manufacturing process for all BIW parts because doing so allows one to take into account the optimization of capital and tooling requirements that may result when similar BIW parts are properly grouped and are manufactured in the same production facility. In addition, on a specific-part basis, other manufacturing technologies meeting both cost reduction potential and technical requirements need further consideration to explore the economic viability potential of a complete carbon-reinforced composite BIW.

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